

HARNESSING CARBON DIOXIDE (CO₂): A CRUCIAL FACTOR IN ATTAINING ZERO EMISSIONS AND ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY IN THE 21ST CENTURY

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ABSTRACT

As the global community intensifies efforts to combat climate change, the role of carbon dioxide (CO₂) management has emerged as a pivotal factor in the journey toward zero emissions and sustainability. This paper explores the innovative approaches to harnessing CO₂, transforming it from a significant greenhouse gas into a valuable resource [1, 2]. By examining the latest advancements in carbon capture, utilization, and storage (CCUS) technologies, this research underscores the potential of these strategies to mitigate climate change while supporting sustainable economic growth. The study also evaluates the policy frameworks and economic incentives necessary to scale these technologies globally, highlighting the integration of CO₂ harnessing in the broader context of circular economy principles. The findings suggest that the effective management of CO₂ is not only essential for achieving net-zero emissions but also for fostering a sustainable future that balances environmental, social, and economic objectives.

This paper aims to contribute to the discourse on sustainable development by presenting CO₂ harnessing as a cornerstone in the 21st-century strategy for addressing climate change and promoting long-term ecological balance.

Keywords: Carbon Dioxide (CO₂), Environmental Sustainability, Zero Emissions, Global Climate Change, Greenhouse Gases, Carbon Sequestration, Carbon Storage.

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INTRODUCTION

Global climate change, driven primarily by the accumulation of greenhouse gases (GHGs) in the atmosphere, poses a significant threat to the environment, economies, and human well-being. Among these gases, carbon dioxide (CO₂) is the most prevalent, accounting for approximately 76% of global GHG emissions [3, 4]. The rise in CO₂ levels, mainly due to the combustion of fossil fuels, deforestation, and industrial processes, has led to an increase in global temperatures, causing more frequent and severe weather events, rising sea levels, and disruptions to ecosystems [5].

To mitigate these impacts, there is an urgent need to reduce CO₂ emissions and ultimately achieve a net-zero carbon footprint. Net-zero emissions refer to the balance between the amount of greenhouse gases emitted and the amount removed from the atmosphere. Achieving this balance is essential for limiting global warming to 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels, as stipulated in the Paris Agreement [6, 7]. One of the key strategies in this effort is harnessing CO₂—capturing it from industrial sources or directly from the air, and either storing it underground or converting it into useful products [8].

This review explores the critical role of CO₂ harnessing in achieving zero emissions and sustainability in the 21st century. It examines current technologies for CO₂ capture, the potential uses of captured CO₂, the challenges faced by these technologies, and future prospects for innovation.

The Role of CO₂ in Climate Change

Carbon dioxide is the primary greenhouse gas emitted through human activities, such as the burning of fossil fuels (coal, oil, and natural gas) for energy and transportation, and through deforestation. Since the Industrial Revolution, CO₂ concentrations in the atmosphere have risen from about 280 parts per million (ppm) to over 415 ppm today [9, 10]. This increase has been the main driver of global warming, with significant consequences for the Earth's climate system.

Rising temperatures have led to the melting of polar ice caps and glaciers, causing sea levels to rise. This not only threatens coastal communities but also disrupts marine ecosystems. Additionally, higher temperatures have resulted in more frequent and severe weather events, such as hurricanes, droughts, and wildfires [11, 12]. The impacts of climate change are already being felt globally, and they are expected to intensify unless significant actions are taken to reduce CO₂ emissions.

Start of Arts

1. Post-Combustion CO₂ Capture

Post-combustion capture is the most widely used CO₂ capture technology, especially in existing power plants. In this method, CO₂ is captured after the fossil fuel has been burned. The flue gas, which contains CO₂ along with nitrogen, water vapor, and other gases, is treated to separate the CO₂. The most common method for post-combustion capture is **amine-based absorption**, where a solvent, typically an amine, is used to absorb CO₂ from the flue gas [13, 14]. The CO₂-rich solvent is then heated to release pure CO₂, which can be compressed and stored. Advances in post-combustion capture focus on improving the efficiency of solvents, reducing energy consumption during the regeneration process, and integrating the technology with existing power plants. New solvents with higher CO₂ absorption capacities and lower regeneration temperatures are being developed to reduce operational costs [15].

2. Pre-Combustion CO₂ Capture

Pre-combustion capture involves the removal of CO₂ before the combustion of fossil fuels. This technology is mainly used in integrated gasification combined cycle (IGCC) plants, where fossil CO (syngas) through gasification [16].

The syngas undergoes a **water-gas shift reaction**, where carbon monoxide reacts with water to form CO₂ and additional hydrogen. The CO₂ is then separated from the hydrogen, typically using physical solvents like Selexol or Rectisol. The remaining hydrogen-rich gas is burned to produce electricity with much lower CO₂ emissions. Advances in pre-combustion capture are focused on improving the efficiency of the gasification process, optimizing the water-gas shift reaction, and developing more effective CO₂ separation technologies. This method is highly efficient but is primarily suited to new power plants due to the complexity and cost of the process [17].

3. Oxy-Fuel (Oxy-CO₂) Combustion

Oxy-fuel combustion involves burning fossil fuels in a mixture of pure oxygen and recycled flue gas, rather than air. This results in a flue gas that is primarily composed of CO₂ and water vapor, making CO₂ capture much simpler. The combustion in pure oxygen produces a high concentration of CO₂ in the flue gas [18]. The water vapor is easily condensed, leaving almost pure CO₂, which can be captured and stored with minimal additional processing. The main challenges for oxy-fuel combustion include the high cost and energy demand of producing pure oxygen, typically through air separation units (ASUs). Recent advancements are focused on improving the efficiency of ASUs, integrating them more effectively with the power generation process, and optimizing the combustion system to handle the higher temperatures associated with pure oxygen combustion [19].

Fig: possible separation techniques in conjunction with the three conditioning processes. [5]

Technologies for CO₂ Capture

The challenge of reducing atmospheric CO₂ levels has led to the development of several technologies aimed at capturing CO₂ from various sources. These technologies vary in their approach, efficiency, and stage of development.

Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS): CCS is one of the most established methods for reducing CO₂ emissions from industrial sources. It involves capturing CO₂ at the point of emission, such as from power plants or factories, and transporting it to a storage site where it is injected deep underground into geological formations. [20] CCS has the potential to reduce CO₂ emissions from large point sources by up to 90%. However, the high costs associated with capturing, transporting, and storing CO₂ have limited its widespread adoption [21].

Direct Air Capture (DAC): Unlike CCS, which targets specific emission sources, DAC involves capturing CO₂ directly from the ambient air. This technology uses chemical processes to bind CO₂ from the atmosphere and concentrate it for storage or utilization. DAC has the advantage of being able to capture CO₂ from diffuse sources, but it is currently energy-intensive and expensive, making it less viable for large-scale deployment without significant advancements in efficiency and cost reduction [22].

Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS): BECCS combines biomass energy production with carbon capture and storage. In this process, CO₂ is captured from the combustion or gasification of biomass, which is considered carbon-neutral because the CO₂ released is offset by the CO₂ absorbed by the plants during their growth. BECCS can result in negative emissions, making it a valuable tool in achieving net-zero or even net-negative emissions [23, 24]. However, concerns about land use, water resources, and biodiversity must be addressed to ensure its sustainability.

Mineralization: Carbon sequestration through mineral reactions involves the binding of CO₂ with naturally occurring minerals to form stable carbonates. This process occurs naturally but can be accelerated through various techniques. [25] Mineralization offers a permanent solution for CO₂ storage, as the carbonates formed are stable over geological timescales. However, the scalability of this approach is currently limited by the availability of suitable minerals and the energy required to accelerate the reaction.

CO₂ Storage

CO₂ storage, also known as carbon sequestration, involves capturing carbon dioxide (CO₂) and storing it in a way that prevents it from entering the atmosphere and contributing to global warming. Here are some key examples of CO₂ storage methods:

1. Geological Storage

- **Depleted Oil and Gas Reservoirs:**

Depleted oil and gas fields are ideal candidates for CO₂ storage. These reservoirs have already held hydrocarbons for millions of years, indicating their ability to contain gases securely over long periods. After the extraction of oil or gas, the remaining space can be used to inject and store CO₂. The infrastructure (such as pipelines and wells) often already exists, making this option cost-effective [26].

- **Saline Aquifers:**

Saline aquifers are porous rock formations that contain saltwater instead of oil or gas. These formations are widespread and have a large capacity for CO₂ storage. CO₂ injected into these aquifers' dissolves in the saline water and can react with minerals in the rock to form stable carbonates, effectively locking away the CO₂ [27].

- **Unmineable Coal Seams:**

Some coal seams are too deep or too poor in quality to be mined economically. These unmineable coal seams can be used to store CO₂. The injected CO₂ can adsorb onto the coal surface, displacing methane, which can then be extracted as an additional energy source. This process is known as CO₂-enhanced coal bed methane recovery (CO₂-ECBM) [28, 29].

2. Mineral Carbonation

- **Natural Mineralization:**

In nature, certain minerals, such as olivine and serpentine, react with CO₂ to form stable carbonates. This process, called mineral carbonation, can be artificially accelerated by exposing these minerals to captured CO₂ [30, 31]. The CO₂ reacts with the minerals to form solid carbonates, which can be stored permanently. This method mimics natural processes but at a much faster rate [25].

- **Industrial Waste Utilization:**

Certain industrial by-products, such as slag from steelmaking, fly ash from coal combustion, or cement kiln dust, can react with CO₂ to form carbonates. By using these materials, CO₂ can be stored in a stable, solid form while also reducing the environmental impact of industrial waste [32].

3. Biological Storage

- **Forests and Afforestation:**

Forests are natural carbon sinks, as trees absorb CO₂ from the atmosphere through photosynthesis and store it in their biomass. Afforestation (planting new forests on lands that have not recently been forested) and reforestation (replanting forests that have been depleted) are strategies for increasing the amount of CO₂ stored in forests.

Sustainable forest management can ensure that these carbon sinks are maintained and even enhanced over time [30, 33].

- **Soil Carbon Sequestration:**

Soils can store significant amounts of carbon in the form of organic matter. Agricultural practices such as no-till farming, cover cropping, and the use of compost or biochar can increase the carbon content of soils. This process not only stores CO₂ but also improves soil health and agricultural productivity [34].

- **Oceanic Storage:**

The oceans naturally absorb CO₂ from the atmosphere, but this process can be enhanced artificially. One approach is to increase the ocean's alkalinity, allowing it to absorb more CO₂. Another method involves the fertilization of certain areas of the ocean with nutrients (such as iron) to stimulate the growth of phytoplankton, which absorbs CO₂ through photosynthesis. However, ocean storage techniques are still largely experimental and come with significant environmental risks, such as ocean acidification and disruption of marine ecosystems [35].

4. CO₂ Utilization with Storage (CCU-S)

- **Carbonate Minerals for Construction:**

Captured CO₂ can be used to produce construction materials, such as concrete, through a process known as CO₂ curing or carbonation curing. In this process, CO₂ reacts with calcium silicates in cement to form stable calcium carbonates, which strengthen the concrete and store CO₂ permanently. This method is particularly attractive because it provides a commercial use for CO₂, reducing the overall cost of capture and storage [36].

- **Synthetic Fuels with Sequestration:**

Synthetic fuels, such as methanol or hydrocarbons, can be produced from captured CO₂ and hydrogen derived from renewable energy. While the use of these fuels eventually releases CO₂ back into the atmosphere, their production can be coupled with permanent storage options to achieve a net reduction in emissions [37]. For example, some carbon capture and utilization (CCU) processes incorporate geological storage as part of the overall system, ensuring that a portion of the captured CO₂ is permanently sequestered.

5. Enhanced Oil Recovery (EOR)

- **CO₂-Enhanced Oil Recovery:**

In EOR, CO₂ is injected into depleted oil fields to increase the amount of oil that can be extracted. The CO₂ reduces the viscosity of the oil and helps to push it towards the production wells. After the oil is extracted, the CO₂ can remain stored in the reservoir. EOR is a mature technology and has the dual benefit of increasing oil production while storing CO₂. However, the environmental benefit depends on how much CO₂ is ultimately stored compared to the emissions from the additional oil produced [38].

UTILIZATION OF CAPTURED CO₂

Once CO₂ is captured, it can be stored underground or utilized in various ways to create value-added products. CO₂ utilization not only helps reduce emissions but also creates economic opportunities.

CO₂ to Fuels: Captured CO₂ can be converted into synthetic fuels through processes such as Fischer-Tropsch synthesis or by reacting with hydrogen produced from renewable energy sources. These fuels can be used in existing infrastructure, such as vehicles and power plants, thereby reducing the need for fossil fuels [39]. The challenge lies in making these processes economically competitive with conventional fuel production.

CO₂ in the Chemical Industry: CO₂ can be used as a feedstock for the production of chemicals such as methanol, urea, and polymers. Methanol, for instance, is a versatile chemical that can be used as a fuel, solvent, or feedstock for producing other chemicals. CO₂-based polymers are another promising area, as they offer a way to create sustainable materials while sequestering CO₂. However, the chemical industry requires high purity CO₂, which adds to the cost and complexity of utilizing captured CO₂ [40].

Enhanced Oil Recovery (EOR): In EOR, captured CO₂ is injected into oil reservoirs to increase the extraction of oil. This process not only boosts oil production but also stores CO₂ underground. While EOR is commercially viable, its association with increased oil production raises concerns about its overall impact on emissions. The net effect depends on the balance between the additional CO₂ captured and stored and the emissions from the additional oil produced [41].

CO₂ in Agriculture and Food Industry: CO₂ is used in greenhouses to enhance plant growth, as higher CO₂ concentrations can increase photosynthesis rates. This can lead to higher yields of crops such as tomatoes, cucumbers, and lettuce. Additionally, CO₂ is used in algae cultivation, which can be used for food, biofuels, and other bioproducts. The integration of CO₂ utilization into the agricultural sector offers a way to reduce emissions while supporting food production and bioenergy [42].

CHALLENGES AND BARRIERS TO CO₂ HARNESSING

Despite the potential of CO₂ capture and utilization technologies, several challenges and barriers must be overcome to achieve large-scale deployment.

Economic Barriers: The high cost of CO₂ capture, transportation, and storage remains a significant barrier to the widespread adoption of these technologies. While advances in technology have reduced costs, they are still not competitive with conventional fossil fuel-based processes. Market incentives, such as carbon pricing or subsidies, are needed to make CO₂ harnessing economically viable [43].

Technical Barriers: The efficiency and scalability of CO₂ capture technologies are critical to their success. Current technologies, particularly DAC, require significant energy inputs, which can offset the benefits of capturing CO₂ [44]. Additionally, the infrastructure needed for CO₂ transportation and storage is lacking in many regions, posing logistical challenges.

Policy and Regulatory Challenges: The regulatory framework for CO₂ capture, utilization, and storage is still evolving. Clear policies and regulations are needed to provide certainty for investors and developers. Additionally, international cooperation is required to address the global nature of CO₂ emissions and to ensure that efforts to reduce emissions in one region are not offset by increases in another [45].

FUTURE PROSPECTS AND INNOVATIONS

Looking ahead, several emerging technologies and innovations hold promise for improving the efficiency, scalability, and cost-effectiveness of CO₂ harnessing.

Emerging Technologies: Research is ongoing into new materials and processes for capturing and utilizing CO₂. For example, metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) are being explored as highly efficient materials for CO₂ capture due to their large surface area and tunable properties. Additionally, advances in electrochemical and photochemical processes offer potential pathways for converting CO₂ into valuable products with lower energy inputs.

Integration with Renewable Energy: The integration of CO₂ capture technologies with renewable energy sources, such as wind and solar, can help reduce the carbon footprint of these processes. For example, using renewable electricity to power DAC or to produce hydrogen for CO₂ conversion can make these processes more sustainable and economically viable.

Innovations in CO₂ Storage: New approaches to CO₂ storage, such as using CO₂ to produce building materials or integrating it into the production of concrete, offer ways to store CO₂ permanently while creating useful products. Additionally, research into biological storage methods, such as enhancing the carbon sequestration potential of soils and forests, is gaining attention as a way to complement technological approaches.

CONCLUSION

Harnessing carbon dioxide is a critical component of the global effort to achieve zero emissions and sustainability in the 21st century. While significant challenges remain, the development and deployment of CO₂ capture and utilization technologies offer a pathway to reduce emissions, create economic opportunities, and mitigate the impacts of climate change. Continued research, innovation, and policy support will be essential to realizing the full potential of these technologies and achieving a sustainable, low-carbon future.

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